

6G + REFERENCE

6G Hardware Enablers for Cell Free Coherent Communications and Sensing

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6G-REFERENCE envisions a future where urban areas are equipped with **sustainable solutions** that can cope with the ever-increasing **traffic demands and population densification**, while providing disruptive capabilities like the materialization of the internet of sense.

The 6G-REFERENCE project **targets practical integrated circuits (IC) and antenna systems for 6G applications**. 6G-REFERENCE will:

Explore radio system operation in the 10-15GHz range

Develop hardware concepts and show feasibility in CMOS

Use additive manufacturing for antenna arrays and nanotechnology for sensors

Our Challenges

Accurate synchronization among distributed radio units (cell-free deployments)

Fronthaul data distribution

Low complexity/cost/ consumption radios

Integration of sensing capabilities

Coexistence with other services

Our Use Cases

Immersive communications

Time sensitive network applications

Integrated sensing and localization

6GSNS

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